

An overview of activities and skills attained from ONS Lab management, from operation and continuous evolution of ADRENALINE testbed, and from prototyping of optical transmission systems

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1. INTRODUCTION

The scope of this manuscript is to present the main activities carried out and the know-how acquired by Msc. Javier Vilchez, Researcher of the Optical Network and Systems (ONS) Department. The management of the facilities and the maintenance of the equipment in the ONS Lab are described in Section 2. Research activities and skills attained from the operation, maintenance and continuous evolution of ADRENALINE testbed are presented in Section 3. In Section 4, the design, development, assembly and experimental validation of fiber-optic transmission systems with the interfaces for control plane are described. Finally, conclusions and interests for the future are presented in Section 5.

2. MANAGEMENT OF THE ONS LAB FACILITIES AND MAINTENANCE OF EQUIPMENT

The ONS Lab was formerly composed of rooms 0.03-0.04, inside the CTTC B4 building. Some actions had to be undertaken to provide this space with constant air conditioning temperature and with ESD protection for the raised floor carpet and for the workbenches, in order to perform research activities in a safe way for both researchers and equipment. Furthermore, skills for the deployment of fiber-optic links between different rooms were attained. In 2015, the room 0.02 was integrated into the ONS Lab to satisfy the requirements for the deployment of the Experimental Platform for Optical-OFDM Systems (EOS platform), under the umbrella of ADRENALINE testbed. In that infrastructure project, the Optical transmission and subsystems lab (Fig. 1), many efforts were done for the planning and execution of different phases in the correct order (e.g., installation of concrete pillars in optimal locations, logistics for the installation of an optical table, dimensioning and installation of electrical, network and fiber optic connections).

Fig 1. Distribution of the Optical transmission subsystems lab (Left) and final aspect (Right)

Other kind of activities carried out are the acquisition of new equipment, according to CTTC internal procedures and laws for public sector, and the management of inventory lists, continuously updated, in order to undergo national and European audits and issues related to insurance policies and claims. Furthermore, an annual maintenance plan is executed year after year, in order to detect and correct anomalies in the operation of all the instrumentation involved in project execution.

3. OPERATION, MAINTENANCE AND CONTINUOUS EVOLUTION OF ADRENALINE TESTBED

A continuous research conducted by the ONS Department with experimentation on different topics of optical transmission has converged on the deployment and continuous evolving of the ADRENALINE testbed multiplatform. During ten years, he has been involved, in a very remarkable way, in the continuous operation, maintenance and evolution of DWDM Metro/Core network (Fig. 2-right). For instance, he planned and executed the migration from a 3-node optical network with ring architecture

(Phase I) towards a 4-node meshed optical network (Phase II). Nowadays, he is carrying out the steps for the migration of the fixed-grid DWDM Metro/Core network to provide it with some enhancements in the architecture of the nodes, and with a flexi-grid optical link. This new architecture (i.e., Phase III) is necessary for the experimental research conducted in the framework of H2020 projects, offering IoT and 5G end-to-end services. In all the phases of migration, the hardware abstraction layer (i.e., hardware controller API from the control plane) is also one of his main interests. Regarding the operation of the network, he has performed experimental demonstrations and explanations to many visiting companies, researchers or institutions; and he is co-author in almost forty publications that involve experimental validations using the fixed/flexi-grid DWDM metro/core network with the S-BVTs developed with the EOS platform of ADRENALINE. Along all those years, he has also obtained know-how in maintenance tasks of software and hardware components in the different platforms of ADRENALINE.

4. DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT, ASSEMBLY AND EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT OF OPTICAL TRANSMISSION SYSTEMS PROTOTYPES

The continuous evolution of ADRENALINE implies the design, development and assembly for new prototypes of transmission systems (Fig. 2) to be integrated within the Metro/Core transport network. The methodology for the design is focused on the integration of commercially available low level components, and the conception of a functional architecture and block diagram for the whole subsystem. The PCB can be assembled in rack-mount chassis, provided with front and rear panels designed according to the physical interfaces, push-buttons and visual indicators considered. All prototypes assemble a microcontroller so that they can be managed by the control plane remotely. In addition, within this context, he is currently one of the CTC supervisors for project in OIS2018 program.

Fig 2. Examples of optical transmission systems (Left and Centre) already integrated in the Metro/Core transport network of ADRENALINE (Right)

In order to implement DSP-enabled programmable optical transceiver solutions within the continuous evolving EOS platform, direct-detection and coherent opto-electronic front-ends are designed and assembled for sliceable bandwidth variable transmitters (S-BVTx) and receivers (S-BVRx), Fig 3 illustrates some examples of opto-electronics developed by the integration of several components, and devices.

Fig 3. Examples of opto-electronic front-ends: for coherent transmitter with dual polarization (Left), and for coherent receiver with dual polarization (Right)

5. CONCLUSIONS AND INTERESTS FOR THE FUTURE

This manuscript has presented some examples of the main activities carried out by Msc. Javier Vílchez. In case of acceptance, this work should be presented in a poster. As interests for the future, the design of Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs) could be introduced in the ONS Department; an external provider could be in charge of manufacturing such kind of devices. Through an alignment station to be purchased, the manufactured PICs could be connected to ADRENALINE.